

ECONOMIC - ORGANIZATIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE PUBLIC TOURISM IN CAMPANIA, ITALY: MANAGEMENT AND HUMAN ASSET ISSUES

Alfonso Marino* & Paolo Pariso*

*University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli", Italy

Abstract: The study intends to analyze the change of management culture within the Campania Public Tourism Sector (CPTS). The aim of the study is to evaluate, through the SWOT analysis, the elements that are relevant to the change of the system logic from bureaucratic to competitive. The differences are explained in figures n. 2 and n. 3 and tables 3 and 4. New young managers working in the CPTS have both theoretical skills and operative knowledge. Theoretical skills are related to education and training (non-humanistic). Managers entering the CPTS have also gained operative knowledge of innovative financial services. This knowledge represents a strong discontinuity with the bureaucratic culture that has characterized the CPTS for a long time, resulting in a negative performance of the business model of human and financial assets. The CPTS offers an ample chance for experimentation. Its strength is linked to the richness of natural, historical and cultural heritage assets of Campania region. On the other side, the organizational bottlenecks and the high incidence of political decision makers constitute the sector's negative features. A competitiveness-enhancing reform related to professional skills, management capabilities and training needs to be started but the process is still in progress.

Keywords: Italian Public Tourism Sector, Campania, Tourism management, Organizational analysis, Human assets

Introduction

From the SWOT analysis, the authors consider the change of the system logic from bureaucratic to competitive. CPTS has been characterized, for the last ten years, by old managers with a humanistic culture and a long presence in CPTS. CPTS was based on three pillars:

- a) National laws;
- b) Local political references;
- c) Local Government Budgeting.

In section one, organizational theories and their impact and evolution in Italy are outlined. Recently, Italian public institutions started to pay attention to business organization and its theories and felt a need for a different approach in the reorganization of the public sectors and subsectors. Italian public tourism sector and Campania's one in particular are illustrated in sections two and three respectively. The

sector workforce of Campania (20,367 units) is second only to Lazio, consists of 70% female university graduates with a degree in social sciences or law. Staff's average professional experience is around 20 years. In relation to the workforce, there is a strong element of discontinuity from the past. As it will be better described in "Finding and Discussion" section, change of management culture within the CPTS is due to young new managers with organizational and managerial education, management innovation skills and training in new innovative companies. Young managers represent the new culture, a striking tool that marks the beginning of a change from a bureaucratic logic to a competitive one. Managers entering the CPTS have also gained operational knowledge of innovative financial services. The innovative knowledge represents a strong discontinuity with the bureaucratic culture that has long characterized the CPTS, resulting in a negative performance of the business model of human and financial assets management.

Literature Review

In English speaking countries, scholars like (Merton, 1949), (Blau, 1971), (Scott, 1964), (Selznick, 1953) (March 1965), (Etzioni, 1964) became eminent organization theorists. The process of diversification of organization theory began in the 1960s thanks to the contributions of (Gouldner, 1954), (Thompson, 1967), (Perrow, 1969, 1988, 1992) in USA, (Woodward, 1975) in UK, (Crozier and Touraine) in France. Works like "Handbook of organizations" (March 1965), "Reading Sociology of Organization" (Grusky and Miller, 1981), "Administrative Behavior" (Simon, 1947) represent fundamental milestones in the evolution of the discipline. After half a century they are still widely consulted. The organization theory made its way into the major American universities. It acquired the identity of empirical science by combining theory and practice and played an important role in that "Society of organizations", (Prethuis, 1971). Organization theory as discipline also had a robust academic life in the UK like other engineering, economic and psychological disciplines. Just to mention one French example, (Crozier, 1969) successfully developed his work on state bureaucracy from the tradition of Weber's organization theory (1945) and from industrial and labor organization field inaugurated in France by Friedman and Touraine. Crozier influenced the organizational policies of the French Public Administration. The latter claim proved fully misconceived and unfounded because of the fruitful collaboration between March and Cyert, (1963) and March and Simon (1958).

The main reasons for the evolution of the discipline were its institutionalization, the creation of university chairs, the implementation of research programs and the publications in scientific journals. However, despite all this, organization theories remained marginal in the framework of economic organizations and therefore had little or no impact on decisions and actions of governments, entrepreneurs and trade unions. Barley (2008) carried out an empirical study, he concluded that practitioners (professionals, consultants and managers) influenced organization science more than the latter affected the application of the discipline. There was no such dialectic in the Italian context. In Italy, organization theories were influenced by industrial relations and were object of prejudice by the academic and governmental institutions. The beginning of the new century marked a turning point. The long economic crisis and the generation turnover of the ruling class sparked a great interest in the discipline. The

application of business organization theories was important as it influenced national, regional and municipal governments' approach towards the development of vast areas of the country where it is possible to produce wealth or redistribute it avoiding the mistakes of the past.

Methodology

The SWOT Analysis is the methodology applied. It involves the assessment of business organization's internal strengths and weaknesses, its opportunities for growth and improvement and the threats to its survival caused by the external environment. The role of new managers, characterized by different education and training experience, is to find a balance between business organization and external environment and to keep this balance over time. Managers can achieve this balance by evaluating new programs and services aimed at maximizing organizational performance. The SWOT analysis is the preliminary decision-making tool that sets the various steps of the work. Step 1 of the SWOT analysis involves the collection and the evaluation of key data. In Step 2 of the SWOT analysis, the data collected are sorted into four categories: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. The different steps highlight the differences between the approaches followed by the old and the new managers for the supply of services. Strengths and weaknesses generally stem from factors within the organization, whereas opportunities and threats usually arise from external factors. Step 3 involves the creation of a SWOT matrix for each approach (indicated as bureaucratic and competitive approach) followed by managers. Step 4 involves the incorporation of the SWOT analysis into a decision-making process to determine which services best meet the organization's overall strategic plan.

Overview of the Public Tourism Sector in Italy

The purpose of the public sector is to promote full sustainability, the development of competences and the definition of operators' principles and guidelines. Moreover, regional tourism policy sets out general guidelines and operational plans which must be implemented, monitored and coordinated by public managers. Tourist Public Sector deals with a specific geographical area (national or regional) in which a number of economic entities, public organizations and natural attractions are located and meet the needs and interests of a particular segment of tourist demand.

Natural, archeological and cultural heritage assets of Italy are outstanding. National figures, concerning sites available to tourists can be synthesized as follows:

- a) 3.607 Museums;
- b) 802 Monuments;
- c) 330 Archaeological Sites.

More than 50% are owned and managed by the public sector. If the number of tourists is considered by place typology (DIT 2014), art cities are second only to seaside resorts:

- a) 38% seaside;
- b) 30% artistic Cities, historical interest;
- c) 15% mountain resorts;
- d) 8% lake resorts
- e) 4% hill and various resorts.

Annually, the three most visited public attractions are:

- a) Colosseum, Palatine Hill, Roman Forum, 4,777,969 visitors, 30,423,950 revenue;
- b) Excavations of Pompeii (Campania) 2,233,496 visitors, 16,369,854 revenue;
- c) Uffizi Gallery, (Florence, Tuscany) 1,554,256 visitors, 1,530,346 revenue.

Lazio is the most visited region with its museums, monuments and archaeological sites. It also has the highest number of sector employees. Campania is second for the number of visitors and sector employees (see Graphic 1). However, the excavations of Pompeii which are the most important archeological site in Campania and one of the most visited site in Italy have recently had 12% drops of visitors.

Graphic 1. Number of employees by region

Assetsce: Ministry of Heritage and Culture, MiBAC, 2015

The total number of employees (MiBAC 2014) is 20,367. More than 50% have an employment contract for a fixed period of time or have an atypical contract; men's average age is 51, only 17% of employees are aged between 19 and 29. 51% of the total number of employees are women. Only 3% are university graduates, holding a high-level management position. The Campania case study offers an interesting example of national reality. Campania has museums, monuments, archaeological sites, seaside and artistic and historical places of interest. Employees in the touristic sector are about 17% of the national total.

Case Study: Campania Public Tourism Sector

For the above-described reasons, CPTS is strongly linked to National Public Tourist. Table 1, shows Campania's potential offer in terms of mobility, accommodation and number of tourists. The sector workforce in Campania is only second to Lazio, which includes the capital, Rome. Main statistical data concerning Campania is given in table 1. Despite all these strengths, Campania outlines a negative trend of 28% in revenue

exhibits (tab 1), in most part due to many organizational bottlenecks and weak organization culture. This needs to be taken in consideration due to the complexity of tourist service management. New decision makers started a competitiveness-oriented reform and the SWOT analysis highlights the shift from a bureaucratic to a competitive system.

Table 1: The main statistical data concerning CPTS

Territory		Accommodation	
Area Km ²	13.595.34	Beds	
Resident population	5.831.461	198.234	
Provinces		Public sector beds as % of total (%)	5,7
5			
Municipalities			
551			
Density of inhabitants per Km ²			
428,15			
Mobility		Presence of paying tourists (BCS)	
Airports	2	Total presences	5.368.280
Railway km		Foreign (%)	40,6
1.252		Main nationalities of inbound tourists	
State motorways km		USA - UK - D	
1.285		Average stay (days)	2,1
Highways km		Presence variation 2015/2010	- 11%
383		Total in the south	
Ports		6.699.820	
10		Total in Italy	
		28.602.605	
Gross revenue (BCS)		Sector revenue (BCS)	
State cultural heritage (Euro)		Variation 2015/ 2010	- 15% foreign
31.362.067		Variation 2015/2010	- 13%
Total in the South		domestic	
34.038.022			
Variation 2015/2010	- 28%		
Total in Italy			
135.508.666			

Data elaborated from source: MiBac 2015

Data show (Figure 1) that there are 551 municipalities in Campania and that more than 50 % of them have resident population under 5.000 units. The complexity of the CPTS management is also due to the coexistence of private and public agencies. Public agencies represent only 5.7 % of accommodation but offer most of rail transportation whereas private operators control road and water-way transportation and have 48% of the total of people employed in transportation in Campania. Visitors' number (BCS) highlights the importance of Campania in south Italy but it also shows a decrease in foreign (USA, UK, Germany) tourist presence (-15%) and domestic (-13%) and a 28% revenue loss.

Figure 1 Campania map with tourist references

For more details refer to the interactive site <http://www.cir.campania.beniculturali.it/mappa-dei-luoghi-della-cultura>

Campania has very favorable climate and natural resources. Figure 1 marks the main points of interest excluding Naples, the region's capital. The morphology favors the coastal area where main points of interest are situated. The coast presents four gulfs including the one of Naples which offers an excellent view of one of the active volcanos in continental Europe. Furthermore, secondary volcanic phenomena like hot springs are still present in Neapolitan areas like the Phlegrean Fields. Islands like Ischia, Procida and Capri are quite close, easily accessible via boat or hydrofoil from different parts of the coast and especially Naples port. There are many UNESCO sites throughout the region including the recent addition of Naples's historical city center. However, tourists who distribute wealth when visiting the region also require quality services during their stay. In certain cases, such as Pompeii and Capri natural cultural attractions are complemented by quality services, which are also the result of management, professional skills and staff training. People employed in the tourist sector are 3559, more than 70% are women with university degree in law or social sciences, 20 years is the average job experience. Therefore, these sites are better equipped to tackle legal and bureaucratic issues but are unprepared for management of service. It is also an effect of the lack of training and certain recruitment policies. Employees' selection is often based on political considerations and assessment criteria of candidates do not include knowledge of business administration, management, organization theory or skills, abilities related to service management. This kind of management culture behavior needs to be overcome if CPTS 's performance has to be oriented to improved results. A new reference model (Cooper, Fletcher, Gilbert & Wanhill, 2008) which focuses on management by objectives and by learning should be adopted. Moreover, CPTS should be more customer-centered, managers should act as interpreters of stakeholders' demands (Ritchie, Crouch, 2003), adapting their view to business organization (Davis 1966). Despite the majority of workforce consists of women, on 200 top managers 180 are men, 60% of which have no experience of service provision or sector knowledge. Furthermore, training, courses on organization (Simon 1947), service provision and client approach techniques have either not been offered at all (for the last 9 years) or considered optional at the employees' discretion. These two factors ensured the weak presence of organizational and professional skills, which

have determined 28% revenue loss mentioned in table 1. However, political decision makers started to change their perspective avoiding basing decisions on political criteria only. The new younger generation of decision makers who have a different educational background, theoretical knowledge and professional experience of organization theory started a new trend around mid - 2000 implementing organizational changes and market-oriented decisions. Campania public tourism SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis below synthesizes service supply in table 2.

Table 2: CTPS SWOT Analysis

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presence of 5 Unesco sites - diversified offer (culture, sea, food and beverage, spas) - international attractions: Pompeii, Capri - International Exhibiton and fair facility , Naples - favorable climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - poor service organization - normative based operating procedures - high incidence of politics - poor maintenance or neglect of sites - high level of pollution - crime - an insufficient offer of accommodation and beds
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - availability of structural funds for projects - need to enhance and promote vast areas - improve port system - new decision makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - negative media impact (on poor maintenance in Pompeii) - degradation of culture and organization of reassetsces - environmental degradation of protected areas - difficulty in implementing organizational and cultural innovation

Table 3: SWOT analysis Bureaucratic Magerial Approach (CPTS)

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience; - strong community partnership / collaboration; - Employees feel part of bureaucratic culture; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not dedicated workforce - Existence of previous Human Resources efforts don't offer innovative solutions; - Tools to improve Human Resources activities are not available (e.g. interview guide and training manual) - The managers are linked to work as regulation and certification, as formal role; - A generalist approach to operation manager; - A concentration of offer in certain areas, Naples and Salerno

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve information about practices in human Resources - Improve leadership training for possible advancement; - Identify / tap into staff hidden potentialities; - Could be addressed strategy to expand global operations linked to the services; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of workers with bureaucracy; - Slowly changing process; - Low advantage of opportunities; - presence of investments from illegal revenue - long term emergencies as in waste disposal issues and relative negative media impact

Table 4: SWOT analysis Competitive Managerial Approach (CPTS)

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous quality improvement (test, work); - Proactive management team - linkage between theory and practice - Increased interest of companies for tourist sector - More attention to private funding; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service cannot be oriented only by business culture; - Driving force of business culture on the values of social action;
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The CPTS Managers could improve the distribution of products; - The CPTS Managers could take full advantage of Campania market characterized by food of excellence; - Managers could implement co-branding with manufacturers of food and drink - Strategy to expand global operations linked to the services; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low responsibility for social advocacy of service; - Implementation of cost effective programs which could effect to the quality of services;

The analysis shows a propensity to change from a bureaucratic to a competitive approach so that the region's natural opportunities, heritage and staff potential are more efficiently exploited. Tables 3 and 4 show that there are significant gaps in CPTS. The SWOT analysis of bureaucratic logic (Table 3) highlights many elements of weakness and threat. In the last twenty years, these issues have not been resolved and the seniority of managers seems to represent a strong obstacle to CPTS growth.

The SWOT analysis of competitive logic (Table 4) highlights strengths and opportunities which would make CPTS more competitive by modifying market opportunities. Weaknesses and threats identified in Table 4, could be corrected through interventions to protect public utility (Service cannot be oriented only by business culture; Driving force of business culture on the values of social action) and quality of public service (Low responsibility for social advocacy of service; Implementation of cost effective programs which could affect to the quality of services).

Findings and Discussion

Younger political decision-makers, in recent years, have shown an increasing interest in application of organization theory to public and to CPTS in particular. Organization

theory provides an approach more cost conscious, more inclined to develop corporate culture as changing instrument (Cooper, Fletcher, Fyall, Gilbert, & Wanhill 2008). The first measure, which was implemented to improve services, consists in enhancing its CPTS's competitiveness, complemented by other reforms aimed at increasing autonomy and flexibility of regional administrations. Campania, includes sites that are of "high national interest" which are managed by local government. Local governments must have managerial expertise, specific knowledge of the field and solid financial bases. CPTS is under economic and managerial control of local administrations. Revenues must be used to finance its operations, but local budgets have always needed to be integrated with state funds. Over the last 15 years, CPTS would not have been able to cover production and staff costs without central financing. Furthermore, productivity and incentives alone (Murphy and Murphy, 2004) cannot ensure better quality service. The problem is not exclusively an economic one. Management skills (Cooper, Fletcher, Fyall, Gilbert & Wanhill, 2008), must take into account how service demand is evolving, in order to avoid the difficulties arisen over the last few years. Service supply is result of social interaction between staff needs and users demand. Until recently a bureaucratic logic characterized service management, governments addressed problems by producing normative tools (Cortes, 2008) and failed to meet employees and user's expectations. A challenge for CPTS is to foster competitive (figure 3) culture and to lighten the system of its bureaucratic (figure 2) burden. The main features of bureaucratic culture are illustrated in figure 2:

- a) Management is essentially normative based, older managers without knowledge of changing services;
- b) Politics role in decision-making process;
- c) Budgeting is inefficient not only in terms of quantity but also in expenditure modality, control, integration and coordination.

Over the last 5 years, such consolidated bureaucratic culture brought about the revenue decrease mentioned above. The SWOT analysis shows how the lack of intervention in the managerial skills reorganization and training needs contributed to the weaknesses of the CPTS.

Figure 2 Bureaucratic culture

What can change competitive logic in the CPTS? First step is the open system as shown in figure 3. An open system entails:

- a) Paying more attention to the market;
- b) Changing the human resources culture;
- c) Paying more attention to quality of services supply.

Figure 3 Competitive culture

Paying more attention to the market means ensuring communication, customer knowledge, and market segmentation (Amposta, 2009). A second step is to improve management culture (Schein, 1985), forge better connections between CPTS and its customers. Low quality monitoring resulted in lack of attention to customer care and quality issues. Service (comfort, accuracy security) is important as climate. Is it possible to create an organization that listens to its staff?

The first answer is the open system, starting with its culture and actions. After, it will be possible to endow CPTS of economic and social legitimacy (Dodds and Butler, 2010). Open system means improving economic performance, but also enhancing the value of the service. Service supply pertains to management of organizations whose core business is to set up an intangible process delivered to public. In contrast to most manufacturing organizations, tourist services are typically produced in the presence of the customers, often with considerable participation and interaction with organizational staffs.

Furthermore, in contrast to manufacturing, tourist service delivery requires extensive coordination between front and back office (Goeldner & Ritchie, 2006, Mowforth, Munt, 2009). Evaluation of service supply involves, above all, the use of variables concerning the quality of service, not only variables of efficiency. Attention, must be dedicated to the setting of the monitoring system in order to evaluate service quality as balance between expected and supplied service. The open system (Norman 1984) shows the principal critical bottleneck of service supply. CPTS (Swarbrooke, 2005) must be reinterpreted (WTO, 2014) taking into account service management. Quickly, CPT must change behavior otherwise it will lose its historical pre-eminent position towards any more agile competitive organization, as shown in figure 3. Over the past two years, new managerial leverage moved CPTS competitiveness forward, overcoming the following concrete issues:

Weaknesses

- a) Assets not dedicated workforce;
- b) The existence of previous Human assets efforts does not offer innovative solutions;
- c) The managers linked to work as regulation and certification, as formal role;
- d) A generalist approach to operation manager;

Threats

- a) Identification of workers with bureaucracy;
- b) Slowly changing process;
- c) First results consolidated. Certainly, a turning point in relation to previous management.

Conclusions

Starting from how organization theories have been introduced in Italy, this paper highlights that they remained marginal until 2000 when political decision-makers began to show a serious interest. Italy has a great need of organization theories. Italian public tourism, and especially CPTS, offer ample opportunity for experimentation. The new decision makers initiated a competitiveness-enhancing reform and the analysis of the case of Campania shows a transition from bureaucratic to competitive logic. Change involves professional skills, management capabilities and training needs. First results have been achieved thanks to organization theories approach. More actions must still be performed. Over the past two years, new managerial leverage moved CPTS competitiveness forward, overcoming the following concrete issues:

Weaknesses

- a) Assets not dedicated workforce
- b) Existence of previous Human assets efforts do not offer innovative solutions;
- c) The managers are linked to work as regulation and certification, as formal role;
- d) A generalist approach to operation manager;

Threats

- a) Identification of workers with bureaucracy;
- b) Slowly changing process;

The challenging process of changing from bureaucratic to competitive logic is still in progress, the outcome is uncertain, but it is important to study and apply organization theory. Attention to organization and its theories may trigger a change in academia, but also in national, regional and municipal government's approach, which could help avoiding the mistakes of the past.

REFERENCES

Amposta, J.B. (2009), Looking for environmental excellence in tourist destinations. *Tourismos*, Vol. 4, No.2, pp.91-106.

- Barley S.R., Gordon W.M., & Debra C. G. (2008), Cultures of culture: Academics, practitioners and the pragmatics of normative control, *Studi Organizzativi*, n.2, Franco Angeli.
- Blau P.M., (1971), *The Structure of the Organization*, Basic Books.
- Cortés-J. I. (2008), Which type of tourism matters to the regional economic growth? The cases of Spain and Italy. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, Vol. 10, pp.127-139.
- Cooper, C. Fletcher, J. Fyall, A. Gilbert, D. & Wanhill, S. (2008), *Tourism Principles and Practice*, Fourth Edition, Prentice Hall.
- Crozier M. (1969), *Il fenomeno burocratico*, Etas – Kompass.
- Cyert R.M., March J.G. (1963), *A Behavioral Theory of the Firm*, Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs.
- Davis L.E. (1966), *The design of jobs*, Industrial Relations, n. 6. Department of Italian Tourist (DIT- 2014) data collection 2014
- Dodds, R. & Butler, R. (2010), Barriers to implementing sustainable tourism policy in mass tourism destinations. *Tourismos*, Vol. 5, No.1, pp.35-54.
- Dwyer L., Wickens E., *Event Tourism and Cultural Tourism: Issues and Debates*, Routledge, 2013, New York
- Etzioni A. (1964), *Modern Organizations*, Prentice Hall.
- Gouldner A. (1954), *Patterns of industrial bureaucracy*, The Free press.
- Goeldner, C. & Ritchie, J. (2006), *Tourism: Principles, Practices, Philosophies*. Tenth Edition, Hoboken, Wiley.
- Grusky O., Miller G.A. (1981), *The Sociology of Organizations: Basic Studies*. Second Edition. Edited by. New York: Free Press.
- Helms M.M., Nixon J. (2008), Exploring SWOT analysis – where are we now? A review of academic research from the last decade, *Journal of Strategy and Management*, vol.3 n.3, page 215 – 251.
- March J. G. (1965), *Handbook of Organizations*. Chicago, IL: Rand McNally.
- March J.G., Simon H.A. (1958), *Teoria dell'organizzazione*, Etas.
- Merton R.K. (1949), *Social Theory and Social Structure*, Free Press.
- Ministry of Heritage and Culture, MiBAC, data collection 2015
- Murphy, P.E. (1985), *Tourism: A community approach*. London, Methuen.
- Murphy, P.E. & Murphy, A.E. (2004), *Strategic management for tourism communities: Bridging the gaps*. Clevedon, Aspects of Tourism Series Channel View Publications.
- Mowforth, M. Munt, I. (2009), *Tourism and Sustainability*. Third Edition, Routledge, New York.
- Norman R., (1984), *La gestione strategica dei servizi*, Etas, Bologna
- Perrow C. (1969), *Organizational Analysis: a sociological view*, Tavistock Publications, London.
- Perrow C. (1988), *Le organizzazioni complesse. Un saggio critico*, Franco Angeli.
- Perrow C. (1992), Small-firms network, in Eccles R., Nohria N., “Networks and Organizations”, Harvard Business University Press, Cambridge.
- Prethuis R. (1971), *La società dell'organizzazione*, Rizzoli
- Ritchie, J. R. B. and Crouch, G. (2003), *The Competitive Destination: A Sustainable Tourism Perspective*. Wallingford: CABI Publishers.
- Rapporto sull'Economia della Cultura in Italia (2014), Ministero per i Beni e le Attività Culturali, MiBAC

Simon A.H. (1947), *Administrative behavior*, Wiley, NY
Schein E. (1985), *Organization Culture and Leadership*, Jossey-Bass, San Francisco.
Scott R. W. (1994), *Le organizzazioni*, Il Mulino.
Selznick P. (1953), *TVA and the Grass Roots*, Berkeley and Los Angeles: University of California Press.
Swarbrooke, J. (1999), *Sustainable Tourism Management*. CABI Publishing, New York.
Thompson J.D. (1967), *Organizations in action*, McGraw-Hill.
Wahab, S. & Cooper, C. (2005), *Tourism in the Age of Globalization*. Routledge, New York
Weber M. (1945), *Economia e società*, Edizioni di Comunità, 1968
Woodward J. (1975), *Organizzazione industriale. Teoria e pratica*, Rosenberg & Sellier.
WTO (World Tourism Organization) (2014) *International Tourism Challenged by Deteriorating World Economy*.

Corresponding Author: Professor Alfonso Marino, University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”, Italy. Email: alfonso.marino@unicampania.it